
A Comparative Study Of Work Participation Rate In Ahmadnagar District

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Abstract:

The work participation rate (WRP) for total workers is defined as the percent of total workers to total population. The term 'work' is used in a special sense in the census. That is 'participation in any economically productive activity'. Such participation may be physical or mental in nature. All those who had worked for the major part of the preceding year were recorded as main workers (at least 06 months or 183 days). All those who had not worked at all during the last year were as non-workers (persons engaged in household duties, students, dependents, retired persons, beggars etc.). The census of India considers only workers as economically productive, while rest are considered economically unproductive. The term 'worker' is defined as 'A person who participate physically or intellectually in economically productive occupations or services is considered a worker'. Also, those who are intellectually involved in organizational and managerial work.

Keywords: Work, Workers, Non-workers, Work participation Rate (WPR).

Introduction:

The work participation Rate (WPR) is a distributive mechanism through which macroeconomic gains may percolate down to a large number of lower income households. WPRs in women population has a positive impact on the health and survival of children. WPRs is related to the Economic composition of population, which is an important aspect of the study of population characteristics of the region. Economic status influence directly or indirectly several aspects of population, like Standard of living which includes wage levels, purchasing capacity together collectively influence the standard of living of the people. Various criteria are

used for the determination of economic activities of people. Such as Economically active and non-active population, Type of occupation, their importance and number of people engaged in them. Population of an area positively definitely effects its economic growth. It is because manpower provides human labor essentially needed for economic development and growth of the region. There are considerable variations in work participation rates among the tahsil of the district between rural and urban sectors and also between males and females. Comparative study focuses on total workers in the district to the state.

Study Area:

Ahmadnagar is the largest district in the Maharashtra state having 5.66% of the area of the state. Ahmadnagar district is located in the somewhat central part of Maharashtra lying between 18⁰2 'N to 19⁰9' North latitudes and 73⁰9'E to 75⁰5' East longitude. Geographical area of the district is 17412 sq. km. The population is 4040642 out of which 3236945 is rural and 803697 is urban population (2001). The area of the district is distributed among 14 sub divisions (Tahsil) for the administrative purpose.

Objective:

1. The present paper has attempted to assess the work participation rate in the Ahmadnagar district and its comparative study to the state of Maharashtra and to the country India.

Database and Methodology:

This study mainly based on secondary data regarding human population, working and non-working population, which is collected from the census handbook of the district. The mathematical techniques like addition, subtraction, multiplication are used for the simple calculations.

Distribution of Workers and Non-Workers (in %): 1991

Sr. No.	Tehsil	% of total workers to total population			% of non-workers to total population		
		P	M	F	P	M	F
01	Nagar	39.02	50.21	26.75	60.98	49.79	73.25
02	Rahuri	44.70	52.00	36.97	55.30	48.00	63.03
03	Shrirampur	39.22	49.20	28.63	60.78	50.80	71.37
04	Newasa	48.90	52.62	44.97	51.10	47.38	55.03
05	Shevgaon	50.18	52.54	47.71	49.82	47.46	52.29
06	Pathardi	50.01	50.12	49.90	49.99	49.88	50.10
07	Jamkhed	49.50	52.31	46.55	50.50	47.69	53.45
08	Karjat	51.55	54.57	48.34	48.45	45.43	51.66
09	Shrigonda	49.52	52.85	46.00	50.48	47.15	54.00
10	Parner	49.80	49.30	50.30	50.20	50.70	49.70
11	Akola	50.19	50.63	49.74	49.81	49.37	50.26
12	Sangamner	46.67	50.05	43.12	53.33	49.95	56.88
13	Kopergaon	43.99	51.38	36.12	56.01	48.62	63.88
	District Total	45.95	51.12	40.50	54.05	48.88	59.50

Source: District Census handbook 1991

The census 1991 recorded 45.95 % of the district population as total workers and 54.05 % as non-workers. The corresponding figures for the state are 42.96 % and 57.02 % respectively. As

compared to 1981 census, there is slightly increase in the work participation rate for the main workers of the district i.e. 41.55 % in 1981 and became 42.47 % in 1991.

Comparative percentage of Workers in the District to the State:

Sr. No.	Workers	Ahmadnagar	Maharashtra
01	Workers	45.95 %	42.96 %
02	Non-Workers	54.05 %	57.02 %

Source: 1991 census record.

As per 1991 census, among the main workers, male participation rate in the district is 51.12 % while that of females is 40.50 %. The corresponding figures for males and females in 1981 are 52.19 % and 30.45 % respectively. It shows that, in 1991 there is decrease in male and increase in female work participation rate of the district.

The proportion of workers is highest in Karjat Tahsil (51.55%) and the

lowest in Nagar Tahsil (39.02%). The district average is 45.95%. The Tahsils of Newasa (48.90%), Shevgaon (50.18%), Pathardi (50.01%), Jamkhed (49.50%), Shrigonda (49.52%), Parner (49.80%), Akola (50.19%), Sangamner (46.67%) shows higher percentage of workers participation than the district average of 45.95%.

Distribution of Workers and Non-Workers (in %) 2001:

Sr. No.	Tahsil	% of total workers to total population			% of non-workers to total population		
		P	M	F	P	M	F
1.	Nagar	38.68	51.55	24.39	61.32	48.45	75.61
2.	Rahuri	49.96	55.60	43.91	50.04	44.40	56.09
3.	3.Shrirampur	40.01	51.66	27.73	59.99	48.34	72.27
4.	Newasa	46.58	53.14	39.57	53.42	46.86	60.43
5.	5.Shevgaon	49.13	52.59	45.50	50.87	47.41	54.50
6.	6.Pathardi	48.27	49.96	46.50	51.73	50.04	53.50
7.	Jamkhed	46.01	51.19	40.56	53.99	48.81	59.44
8.	Karjat	47.65	53.48	41.40	52.35	46.52	58.60
9.	Shrigonda	50.05	54.99	44.77	49.95	45.01	55.24
10.	Parner	53.05	54.29	51.80	46.95	45.71	48.20
11.	Akola	51.84	54.05	49.56	48.16	45.95	50.44
12.	Sangamner	46.31	51.16	41.17	53.69	48.84	58.83
13.	Kopergaon	44.14	51.66	36.04	55.86	48.34	63.95
14.	Rahata	42.37	51.89	32.22	57.63	48.11	67.78
	District Total-	45.96	52.59	38.90	54.04	47.41	61.10

Source: Census of India 2001.

Comparison of Workers and Non-workers to the state,1991 & 2001:

Census Year	Workers %		Non-workers %	
	District	state	District	State
1991	45.95	42.96	54.05	57.02
2001	45.96	42.49	54.04	57.50

The census 2001 recorded 45.96 % of total workers 54.04 % of non-workers. The corresponding figures for the state of Maharashtra are 42.49% and 57.50% respectively. Here district shows more percent of workers than state while state has more percent of non-workers than the District. The census 1991 recorded 45.95% of the district population as total workers and 54.05% as non-workers. Both are increased by 0.01 % only during the 1991-2001 decade. State shoes decrease in workers percentage by 0.47 % and increase in non-workers percent by 0.48 %.

The 2001 census records highest proportion of workers in Parner Tahsil (53.05%) and lowest in Nagar Tahsil (38.68%). The District average is 45.96 %. The Tahsil of Newasa (46.58%), Shevgsan (49.13%), Pathardi (48.27%), Jamkhed (46.01%), Shrigonda (50.05%), Rahuri (49.96%), Akola (51.845), Sangamner (46.31%) shows higher percentage of

Work participation Rate (percent) 1991-2001 :

	Persons		Males		Females	
	2001	1991	2001	1991	2001	1991
India	39.1	37.5	51.7	51.6	25.6	22.3
Maharashtra	42.5	43.0	53.3	52.2	30.8	33.1
Ahmadnagar	45.96	45.95	52.59	51.12	38.90	40.56

Conclusion:

- 1) In 1991, decrease in male and increase in female work participation rate.
- 2) In 2001, work participation rate is increased by 0.01%. There is increase in male and decrease in female work participation rate. In Maharashtra, WPR

workers participation than the district average of 45.96 %.

Among the workers, male participation rate is 52.59 % and female 38.90 %. While workers male participation rate in rural area of the district is 53.17 % and female is 44.55 %. The proportion of female workers is lower than that of male in rural (44.55%) and urban (15.65%) because females are attending their household duties.

The work participation rate of the district was 50.27 % in 1961, which decreased to become 35.43 % in 1971. It shows increasing trend from 1971 to 2001. In 1981 it became 45.68 %, which is increased by 10.25% during the decade. Then it is slightly increased by 0.27% to form 45.95% in 1991 and very slightly increased by 0.01% to form 45.96% in 2001. Some what similar trend is found among the male and female work participation in the district.

decreased by 0.5%. There is increase in male and decrease in female work participation rate.

- 3) India on an average, has comparatively low participation rate (39.1%) in consonance with the stage of its demographic transition. while 51.7% of

the country's male population was engaged in economically gainful activities, the corresponding figure for female was only 25.6%. It means that while one among every two males in the country was a worker, in case of females the corresponding ratio was one among every four females. The work participation rate among females in India continued to be low because of 1) Continuing prejudices against female participation in outdoor activities among certain sections of Indian society. 2) comparatively low literacy rate among females 3) Limited availability of jobs suitable for females and 4) Competition among males and females for jobs which still remain extremely limited under the prevailing conditions of unemployment.

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